

GROWTH PERFORMANCE OF TURMERIC (*Curcuma longa* L.) UNDER VARIOUS SPECIES OF BAMBOO-BASED AGROFORESTRY SYSTEM IN EASTERN VIDARBHA REGION

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Abstract

Bamboo is a woody grass that growing fast and yields consistent income after three years of growth and thus harvesting of mature culms allows for the addition of light and other climatic microclimate elements, making it ideal for shade loving crop like turmeric and zinger in current study Waigaon variety of turmeric (*Curcuma longa* L.) was cultivated as cover crop at 30 cm x 30 cm spacing under eight different bamboo species viz., *Bambusa vulgaris*, *Dendrocalamus longipathus*, *Bambusa tulda*, *Bambusa cacherensis*, *Dendrocalamus stocksii*, *Bambusa polymorpha*, *Bambusa balcoa*, *Dendrocalamus strictus* plantations (7m x 2m) and in open field i.e. without bamboo at the research farm of All India Co-ordinate Research Project (AICRP) on Agroforestry, Futala, College of Agriculture, Nagpur, (MH) in 2024-25. The experiment laid out in Randomize block design (RBD) with 9 treatments and 3 replications. The study on growth and morphological parameters of turmeric crop revealed that the significant variation among different bamboo based agroforestry system. The turmeric plants grown under *Bambusa balcoa* + Turmeric (T7), *Bambusa tulda* + Turmeric (T8) and *Bambusa vulgaris* + Turmeric (T1) showed superior growth in terms of plant height, number of leaves, leaf length and leaf width as compared to plants grown under other species of bamboo and sole turmeric. Whereas, the maximum number of tillers per plant was shown in Turmeric (control) (T9). Among the different bamboo-turmeric based treatments the significantly highest average collar diameter was 7.42 mm showed in *Bambusa polymorpha* + Turmeric (T6).

Key words - Agroforestry system, Turmeric, Bamboo, Growth

Introduction

Agroforestry refers to land-use systems that integrate trees, arable crops and animals on a same unit of land. These systems provides multiple benefits including fuel, food, fodder and timbers to the farmers. They also help in fulfilling national commitments to international goals. As a result, agroforestry is a balanced, integrated and widely used land-use agricultural method (Deshmukh *et al.*, 2023). Moreover, multiple studies indicate that agroforestry is more profitable than either forestry or agriculture alone (Chaturvedi, 1981; Lahiri, 1983; Mathur *et al.*, 1984; Chandra, 1986; Patel, 1988). Thus, peoples are more likely to adopt agroforestry system when short rotation woody species because the woody component can yield returns quickly.

Agroforests including bamboos have a great deal of potential to support the economic growth of poor nations in tropical regions, while also ensuring food and nutritional security. Bamboo is a huge, woody and very fast growing perennial grass that belongs to the family Poaceae (Chapman, 1996). Bamboo is often referred to as "poor man timber," it is essential for raising the socio-economic standing of people living in rural areas. Millions of people in India rely on bamboo for their livelihood and it is a major contributor to the country's economy.

Treatment Details

Treatments	Treatment Details
T ₁	<i>Bambusa vulgaris</i> + Turmeric
T ₂	<i>Dendrocalamus longipathus</i> + Turmeric
T ₃	<i>Bambusa tulda</i> + Turmeric
T ₄	<i>Bambusa cacherensis</i> + Turmeric
T ₅	<i>Dendrocalamus stocksii</i> + Turmeric
T ₆	<i>Bambusa polymorpha</i> + Turmeric
T ₇	<i>Bambusa balcoa</i> + Turmeric
T ₈	<i>Dendrocalamus strictus</i> + Turmeric
T ₉	Turmeric (Control)

Results and Discussions

Effect of bamboo-based agroforestry system on growth parameters of turmeric crop

The growth parameters of turmeric are crucial as they directly impact on impact on production of turmeric. The bamboo-based agroforestry

The perennial herbaceous plant known as turmeric (*Curcuma longa* L.) belongs to the Zingiberaceae family. It is a shade loving rhizomatous crop is suitable to cultivate as cover crop (Kumar and Naugraiya, 2020). The present study was conducted to work out the growth and yield performance of cover crop of turmeric under various species of bamboo plantation as Agroforestry system.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted at research farm of All India Co-ordinate Research Project (AICRP) on Agroforestry, Futala, College of Agriculture, Nagpur, (MH) during kharif season of 2024-25. The research site has sub-tropical climate with dry conditions prevailing for most of the year and the average annual rainfall of 1064.10 mm. The mean annual temperature of region is 25.90 °c. The experiment was set up using a randomized block design (RBD) with 9 treatments and 3 replications. The eight different species of bamboo plantation was 4 years old with spacing of 7 m x 2 m and turmeric was cultivated as cover crop at 30 cm x 30 cm spacing between rows of eight different bamboo species and also in open plot for reference. As per the plot size each parameter growth and yield parameter of turmeric was recorded. The results obtained was statistically analyzed as per methods suggested by Gomez and Gomez (1984).

systems create a unique microenvironment that significantly influences the growth of turmeric. The turmeric being a shade tolerant rhizomatous crop generally responds positively to the moderate light condition that provided by bamboo plantations. The data from Table 1. revealed that the plant height, number of leaves per plant, leaf length,

leaf width, number of tillers per plant and collar diameter of turmeric crop.

Plant height (cm)

Plant height of turmeric crop was shown statistically significant effect on bamboo-based agroforestry system. The highest average plant height of turmeric crop was observed in treatment T7- *Bambusa balcooa* + Turmeric (83.23 cm) than other treatments which was

followed by T3- *Bambusa tulda* + Turmeric (81.87 cm) and T1- *Bambusa vulgaris* + Turmeric (81.30 cm) and lowest average plant height of turmeric crop was measured in treatment T5- *Dendrocalamus stocksii* + Turmeric (72.73 cm). This implied that as compared to sole cropping the plant height of turmeric was shown to increase significantly in a bamboo-based agroforestry system (Sharangi *et al.*, 2022).

Table 1. Effect of bamboo-based agroforestry system on growth parameters of turmeric crop

Treatments	Growth parameters of turmeric crop					
	Plant height (cm)	No. of leaves per plant	Leaf length (cm)	Leaf width (cm)	No. of tillers per plant	Collar diameter (mm)
T1	81.30	13.37	46.63	18.83	1.48	5.91
T2	75.27	12.10	45.43	17.40	1.70	6.65
T3	81.87	13.97	47.27	19.33	1.39	6.45
T4	78.80	12.90	45.67	18.33	1.45	7.09
T5	72.73	11.40	44.20	16.17	2.15	5.20
T6	76.90	13.17	45.60	17.57	1.63	7.42
T7	83.23	14.13	47.47	19.40	1.37	6.71
T8	74.10	11.97	44.67	17.23	1.97	5.68
T9	72.23	11.83	44.40	16.30	2.38	5.36
'F' - Test	Sig	Sig	Sig	Sig	Sig	Sig
SE(m)±	0.3905	0.2717	0.1965	0.2168	0.2225	0.2446
C.D. at 5%	1.1709	0.8148	0.5893	0.6501	0.6673	0.7335
CV (%)	0.8741	3.6896	0.7449	2.1052	22.3481	6.7530

Fig 1: Effect of bamboo-based agroforestry system on plant height of turmeric crop

Number of leaves per plant

The leaves are necessary for photosynthesis and contribute to the biomass of plant, the number of leaves per plant is crucial predictor of the ultimate growth and productivity of a plant. Formation of number of leaves showed statistically significant effect on bamboo-based agroforestry system. The treatment T7- *Bambusa balcooa* (14.13) has more leaves compared to all other treatments, whereas T5- *Dendrocalamus stocksii* (11.40) has fewer leaves. This increase in number of leaves under the bamboo canopy is probably a result of the shade that the bamboo species provides (Meenakshi 2024).

Leaf length

The growth of leaf length of turmeric crop showed statistically significant effect on bamboo-based agroforestry system. In comparison to other treatments, treatment T7- *Bambusa balcooa* + Turmeric (47.47 cm) showed significantly higher leaf length, which was comparable to treatments T3- *Bambusa tulda* + Turmeric (47.27 cm) and T2- *Bambusa vulgaris* (46.63 cm) and lowest leaf length was recorded in treatment T5- *Dendrocalamus stocksii* + Turmeric (44.20 cm).

Leaf width

The growth of leaf width of turmeric crop showed statistically significant effect on bamboo-based agroforestry system. In comparison to other treatments, treatment T7- *Bambusa balcooa* + Turmeric (19.40

cm) showed significantly higher leaf width, which was comparable to treatments T3- *Bambusa tulda* + Turmeric (19.33 cm) and T2- *Bambusa vulgaris* + Turmeric (18.83 cm) and lowest leaf width was recorded in treatment T5- *Dendrocalamus stocksii* + Turmeric (16.17 cm). This may have occurred due to shade of bamboo species, as turmeric plants thrive under shady environments prefer to expand their leaf surface area in order to absorb more light and fulfill their photosynthetic requirements. Similar result was reported by Debata and Das (2024) noted that the leaf length and width of turmeric crop was significantly higher when intercropped with pigeon pea.

Number of tillers per plant

The formation of tillers per plant showed statistically significant effect on bamboo-based agroforestry system. The maximum number of tillers per plant of turmeric crop was found under treatment T9- Turmeric (control) (2.38) followed by treatment T5- *Dendrocalamus stocksii* + Turmeric (2.15) and T8- *Dendrocalamus strictus* + Turmeric (1.97) and minimum number of tillers per plant found under T7- *Bambusa balcooa* + Turmeric (1.37) followed by treatment T3- *Bambusa tulda* + Turmeric (1.39). The sole cropping was observed maximum number of tillers per plant as compared to bamboo-based agroforestry system this might be due to sun light intensity and duration in open field was higher as compared to agroforestry systems. The according to Lalitha

Bai (1981) the amount of shade had a detrimental influence on tillering of plant.

Collar diameter

The collar diameter of plant is crucial predictor of the ultimate growth and productivity of a plant. The effect of bamboo-based agroforestry system on collar diameter of turmeric plant showed statistically significant. The maximum collar diameter was observed in treatment T6- *Bambusa polymorpha* + Turmeric (7.42 mm) followed by treatment T4- *Bambusa cacherensis* + Turmeric (7.09 mm) and minimum was observed in treatment T5- *Dendrocalamus stocksii* +

Turmeric (5.20 mm) followed by treatment T9- Turmeric (Control) (5.36 mm). The collar diameter of turmeric crop was increased much faster in agroforestry system than open condition. This may be occurred due to shade provided by bamboo species, as turmeric plants grow under shady environments prefer to expand their collar surface area in order to transport more food and water to whole plant and fulfil their needs. The similar result was reported by Lal *et al.* (2019) the collar diameter of ginger crop was increased in bamboo-based agroforestry system as compared to monocropping.

Fig 2: Effect of bamboo-based agroforestry system on Collar diameter of turmeric crop

Conclusion

As cover crop of turmeric under various bamboo species was significantly influenced the growth of turmeric crop. Most of the growth parameters including plant height, number of leaves, leaf length, leaf width and collar diameter of turmeric crop performed better under bamboo based agroforestry system as compared to other system due to turmeric plants thrive under shady environments. While the number of tillers per plant was significantly highest in open field as compared to agroforestry systems.

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References

1. Chandra, J. P. 1986. Poplar a cash crop for North Indian Farmers. Indian Forester, 112 (8): 698-710.
2. Chapman, G. P. 1996. The biology of grasses. Department of Biochemistry and Biological Sciences, Wye College, University of London, U.K. pp 14-19.
3. Chaturvedi, A. N. 1981. Popular farming in U.P. (India). U.P. Forest Bulletin No. 45.
4. Debata D. K. and Das L. K. 2024. Performance of Turmeric (*Curcuma longa* L) and Pigeon pea (*Cajanus Cajan* L.) Intercropping System under North Eastern Ghat Zone of Odisha, India. Journal of Scientific Research and Reports, 30(4): 179-186.
5. Deshmukh, H., Dobriyal, M., Tandel, M. B., Gunaga, R., Sharma, O. P., Garde, Y. A., Thakare, U., Kunwar, R.,

6. Gomez, K. A., Gomez, A. A. 1984. Statistical procedures for agricultural research. 2nd ed. New York: John Wiley & Sons; c1984. p. 680.
7. Lahiri, A. K. 1983. Agroforestry in West Bengal, Part I and II. In: Proceedings of workshop on Agroforestry, Karnal, (Mathur RS, Gogate MG ed) pp. 218-225.
8. Lal, J. and Naugraiya, M. N. 2019. Performance of Ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) under Bamboo (*Dendrocalamus strictus*) based Agroforestry System in plains of Chhattisgarh. Trend in Bioscience 18, 1-6.
9. Lalitha Bai E K. 1981. Shade response of common rainfed intercrops of coconut. M.Sc. (Agri.) Thesis, Kerala Agricultural University, Thrissur, Kerala, India.
10. Mathur, R. S., Sharma, K. K. and Ansari, M. V. 1984. Economics of Eucalyptus plantation under agroforestry. Indian Forester, 110: 171.
11. Meenakshi K. 2024. Studies on the effect of intercropping, mulching and manurial practices on yield and quality of turmeric (*curcuma longa* l.). Ph.D. Thesis. Dr. Yashwant Singh Parmar University of Horticulture & Forestry Solan (Nauni) HP, 79-80P.
12. Patel, V. J. 1988. A new strategy to high density agroforestry. Jivarajbhai Patel Agroforestry Centre, Surendrabagh, Gujrat, pp.57.
13. Rupesh Kumar and Naugraiya, M. N. 2020. Performance of Turmeric (*Curcuma longa*) under Bamboo (*Dendrocalamus strictus*) based Agroforestry System in Chhattisgarh. International Journal Current Microbiology App. Sci. 9 (06): 4080-4084.
14. Sharangi, A. B., Gowda M. P. and Suddhasuchi Das. 2022. Responses of turmeric to light intensities and nutrients in a forest ecosystem: Retrospective insight.